

Genetic Evaluation and Utilization

HYBRID RICE

Performance of IRRI hybrid rices in Andhra Pradesh

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We evaluated yield potential and heterosis in morphophysiological attributes of 11 IRRI hybrid rice lines in Andhra Pradesh in 1984 dry season. Seeds were sown on 2 Jan and 20-d-old seedlings were transplanted at 20- × 15-cm spacing in a randomized block design with three replications. NPK was

applied at 120-13-25 kg NPK/ha.

The hybrids were compared with IR50, IR54, and IR36 and local BPT1235. Yield components, leaf area index, and harvest index were recorded and heterosis in different characters was calculated based on the performance of the best check, IR36 (see table).

Yield potential of hybrids HR6, HR8, and HR10 was significantly higher than that of IR36 and HR1 performed at par. The other hybrids had high spikelet sterility and low panicle number and harvest index. HR4, HR5, and HR9 yielded 0.8-1.4 t/ha, had high negative heterosis in panicle number and spikelet

fertility and 60-81% spikelet fertility. All the hybrids matured 8-12 d earlier than IR36, which matured in 112 d.

HR6, HR8, and HR10 had significant positive heterosis in yield (11% to 23%) because of positive heterosis in panicle number and spikelets per panicle, grain weight, total biomass, and leaf area index. Heterosis was positive but not significant for harvest index. Almost all the hybrids had negative heterosis in spikelet fertility. Spikelet sterility in general was higher (>30%) even in standard checks, because there were many cloudy days during the crop season. *ℳ*

Standard heterosis for yield and yield components of some hybrid rices, Andhra Pradesh, India.^a

Hybrid no. and parentage	Yield (t/ha)	Standard heterosis (%)							
		Yield	Panicles/m ²	Spikelets/panicle	Spikelet fertility %	1000-grain weight	Total dry matter at harvest	Harvest index	Leaf area index
MR365A/IR13420-6-3-3-1	4.7	+ 7 (NS)	- 4 (NS)	+12 (NS)	-25 (S)	+ 3 (NS)	+40 (NS)	+13 (NS)	+47 (S)
MR365A/IR13525-2-2-3-3-2-2	3.8	-14 (S)	- 4 (NS)	+ 9 (NS)	-27 (S)	+ 1 (NS)	+20 (NS)	+ 7 (NS)	+18 (NS)
IR10179-2-3-1A/IR13524-21-2-3-3-2-2	2.8	-14 (S)	-10 (NS)	+ 2 (NS)	-32 (S)	-10 (S)	-20 (S)	- 3 (NS)	+ 9 (NS)
MR365A/IR18349-22-1-2-1-1	0.8	-82 (S)	-18 (S)	+51 (S)	-73 (S)	+13 (S)	-26 (S)	+ 3 (NS)	+50 (S)
MR365A/IR21015-180-3-3	1.1	-75 (S)	-13 (S)	- 5 (S)	-44 (S)	+13 (S)	+23 (NS)	+ 3 (NS)	+53 (S)
MR365A/IR50	4.9	+11 (S)	+ 5 (NS)	+18 (NS)	-11 (NS)	+19 (S)	+12 (NS)	+13 (NS)	+53 (S)
IR747 B26-3-A/IR50	3.5	-20 (S)	+ 9 (NS)	-18 (NS)	- 3 (NS)	-21 (S)	+20 (NS)	0 (NS)	- 6 (NS)
V20 A/IR9761-19-1	5.0	+14 (S)	+20 (NS)	+ 9 (NS)	+ 1 (NS)	+25 (S)	+40 (NS)	+13 (NS)	+62 (S)
V20 A/IR13419-113-1	1.4	-68 (S)	-14 (NS)	+49 (NS)	-62 (S)	+ 9 (S)	+49 (S)	+10 (NS)	+53 (S)
97A/IR2307-247-2-2-3	5.4	+23 (S)	+33 (NS)	+17 (NS)	- 3 (NS)	+ 9 (S)	+22 (NS)	+13 (NS)	+94 (S)
IR10154-23-3-3A/IR15795-232-33	4.0	- 9 (S)	- 2 (NS)	-12 (NS)	- 4 (NS)	+ 3 (NS)	+ 6 (NS)	- 7 (NS)	+76 (S)
IR36 (check)	4.4								
CD	0.3		49	39	11.1	1.8	0.4	NS	0.5
CV %	4.5		5.2	13.7	9.6	3.8	9.1	11.3	8.7

^aS = significant, NS = nonsignificant.

Natural outcrossing of cytoplasmic male sterile V20A

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Natural outcrossing of male sterile parents is important for hybrid rice production. In 1982 dry season, the cytosterile line V20A was planted with the maintainer line V20B.

Seed set on cytosterile line V20A in relation to direction and distance from the pollen source, Bogor, Indonesia, 1982 dry season.

Direction	Seed set (%) at given distance from pollen source					Mean seed set (%)
	30 cm	50 cm	70 cm	90 cm	110 cm	
Northwest	14	7	5	7	5	8
Southwest	5	7	7	4	5	6
Northeast	8	7	5	3	3	5
Southeast	5	7	4	5	2	5
Mean	8	7	5	5	4	6

To synchronize flowering, V20A was seeded 3 d earlier and 3 d later than

V20B and transplanted at the same time in an isolated plot at 1 seedling/hill. The